

THE IMPACT OF TEACHERS AND SEVERAL PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS ON THE COVERAGE OF SPEECH BARRIERS

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Abstract. *This article aims to analyze the importance of teachers` role and different types of methods for illumination of psychological issues faced by students in speaking and learning English language. Speaking is the most fundamental skill by which people express their thoughts. Communication is the backbone of our society. Without communication skills, the ability to progress in the contemporary world and in life, itself, would be nearly impossible. Thus, it is vital for teachers to examine even minor problems in speaking so that they can seek for appropriate solutions to them. This preliminary study collected data about challenges in speaking such as lack of confidence, shyness, fear of making mistakes when speaking the English language, lack of motivation in students in speaking the English language or nervous in speaking the English language in public. The finding depicts that most of the vicissitudes are strongly related to psychology, in this paper will be discussed a great number of approaches to overcome speech barriers.*

Keywords: *Academic success, influence, speech barriers, learning environment, poor communication, assessing, motivation, psychology, technique, friends, teachers.*

Introduction

The important role of English is pointed out by Diem who states, "To fulfill the needs of the globalization era, English will take the strategic place in the world." Speaking is a productive skill and also one of the difficult skills, because the foreign language learners must speak and think about components of speaking at the same time. Most students evaluate their success in language learning as well as the effectiveness of their English course on the basis of how much they feel they have improved in their speaking proficiency.

The vast majority of student are not confident about themselves speaking English language in front of people. The teachers have to identify reasons and try to utilize some useful psychological technique for eliminating the speech barriers. Moreover, mentors need to feel responsibility for students who are eager to speak fluently in English, as they play a key role in the improvement of communicative skills in students. The self-confidence and beliefs of the students are completely depending on the teachers. They have to conduct lessons in more informative way, by giving them examples from real life (John W.2012).

Likewise, the teachers can make adequate learning atmosphere with several activities, where learners will be concerned with verbal communication with unfamiliar faces in order to conquer fear. A teacher`s teaching strategy have a strong impact on the progress of students` understanding in language learning in terms of speaking.

Some psychological factors such as shyness and anxiety are considered as the major causes of students` reluctance to speak. With the help of a creative teacher, the

capacity to express one's thoughts, opinions, and feelings, in the form of words put together in a meaning way, provides the speaker with several distinct advantages. Therefore, any gaps in communication result in misunderstandings and problems with the person to communicate with because that person does not understand the message uttered by the speaker.

Being a teacher is not such an easy job. Accordingly, teachers need to fulfill gaps in students' knowledge, for example, typical learner problems might be poor grammar, poor pronunciation, not being able to participate actively in conversation, speaking slowly, and taking too long to compose utterances. (Chaney 1998)

In the modern world, the role of a foreign language in the learning process is significantly increasing. Changes in the socio-cultural context of public life entail a change in the requirements of society for education in general, and for language learning in particular. Often students ask: "Why learn the language?" The question for them is completely natural and simple, but very difficult for the person to whom it is asked.

The main findings and outcomes

For some language learners, speaking in public often causes excitement and anxiety. What if I forgot something? Lost and unable to cope with my emotions? Cannot answer the questions? Maybe my speech will be tedious to the audience.

It is widely believed that almost everyone in their life has faced the problem of public speaking. As a rule, this comes from childhood, when a case of failure at the blackboard is fixed in the subconscious. As soon as you forget a line of a poem or a historical date, silence descends in the class. Everyone looks at you, thoughts in your head are confused, making you feel stressed. In such a situation, you want the ground to open up and swallow you. Then followed either severity from teacher or the ridicule of classmates, and then the brain tightly grasp and fixed the picture of people looking at you, as a result, an increasing feeling of shame and self-doubt. Additionally, something unpleasant happens at that time, your brain remembers that situation, and connects your shame and excitement in your past performance with current one. A negative conditioned reflex in speaking is developed in many people. To this list will be two more dread such as the fear of responsibility and the fear of making a mistake. The more effort a person makes, overcoming his fear, the more he concentrates on it.

Usually, students who spend a lot of time and energy on preparing and studying the material, but precisely because of the fear of public speaking, then they cannot demonstrate the level of their knowledge and preparation. The most effective way is practice. Performance in front of the audience can be a real asset to subside the fear. Preparing in advance your speech might be a good suggestion to be more confident. An educator need to give more attention and motivation to well-speaking in their early age, in order to create a good manner.

Another factor that contributes to the fear of speaking is how skilled you are in this area. While many people consider themselves naturally good speakers, there is always room for growth. The people who work on their skills, instead of relying on natural talent, are the speakers who stand out the most. Increased competence leads to increased confidence which is an effective antidote to fear. While communicating no matter what language, the use of words should be understandable, clear and simple. Besides, during communication, the speaker is required to make effective use of body language.

It is easy for students to speak in a foreign language about topics they are interested in: personal topics and topics close to their lives. The teacher should think about his students` lives and interests when he plans to enhance their speaking skill. It is a good idea to plan two types of activities: one where students practice vocabulary and grammar in a more controlled way, and another type where students can speak fluently.

Conclusion

To sum up, I would say that teachers have a strong influence on learners, and they may give a right direction. With the help of some methods, students can achieve their aim to be a confident speaker. Furthermore, a teacher should attempt to scrutinize problems in their speech and encourage them. Most importantly, students should do their best to improve speaking.

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